

Malala as a Champion of Women in *I Am Malala*

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Abstract

The autobiography "I Am Malala" begins on October 9, 2012, as Malala Yousafzai, a teenaged girl, makes her way to school by bus. On to school, Malala thinks about how her hometown of Mingora, Pakistan has changed in the last decade, and how the Talibans continue to pose a threat to advocates of education and women's rights. Suddenly, a man climbs onboard, raises a gun and shoots Malala in the head. The novel "flashes back" about Malala's rebirth. In her work, Malala explains more about her culture. She is a Pashtun, an ethnic group situated mostly in Afghanistan and Pakistan. She lives in the Swat Valley, a beautiful part of Northwestern Pakistan. She is also a devout Muslim, and has been all her life. From a very early age, she was conscious of the restrictions being placed on women because of feminine gender. Hence, the article ponders over the male chauvinistic life incidents faced by her in the way of a champion of women.

Keywords: Malala, Education, Talibans, Terrorism, Women Emancipation.

Malala's father, Ziauddin, is an appealing, taught man. He grew up examining verse and writing, and earned his family's regard by winning a few renowned discussing rivalries. During the 1980s, when Pakistan fell heavily influenced by the severe despot General Zia, Ziauddin established a progression of schools that offered trainings to young ladies just as young men. While a large number of these endeavors fizzled—since numerous Muslims in Pakistan would not have confidence in a lady's entitlement to training—Ziauddin inevitably discovered achievement. As a grown-up, he wedded Tor Pekai for adoration, instead of due to a family game plan—this, Malala notes, is exceptionally sporadic in Pashtun culture. Ziauddin turned into an enthusiastic promoter with the expectation of complimentary discourse, instruction, and ladies' privileges: three causes that he raised Malala to regard profoundly.

As a youngster, Malala was sharp yet modest. Ziauddin urged her to partake in talking and discussing rivalries, and she did as such, bit by bit stirring her way up to get one of the most gifted open speakers of her age. She exceeded expectations in the homeroom, normally positioning first in her classes. Once, when Malala was around six years of age, she took a toy from her companion, and subsequently built up a propensity for taking different things. At the point when they got some answers concerning this current, Malala's folks were so embarrassed about her that Malala made plans to never take anything or do anything corrupt until the end of time. She guarantees that she never has. Growing up, Malala saw the uncontrolled neediness in her locale. She bothered her dad to enable more youngsters to enter

his school on grant, and Ziauddin concurred. Ziauddin and Tor Pekai raised Malala to be a devout Muslim. In spite of having faith in the Islamic confidence, Malala saw since the beginning that Pakistanis would refer to Islam when they disparaged ladies and prohibited them from learning. Malala started to build up her very own translation of Islam, whereby ladies could instruct themselves while additionally being splendidly unwavering Muslims.

In 2007, Pakistan's circumstance breaks down still further when the Taliban kill Benazir Bhutto, the female leader, and a significant good example for Malala (who is ten years of age at the time). In the consequence of the death, the Taliban turns out to be progressively brutal, exploding schools crosswise over Pakistan that offers instructions to young ladies just as young men. Ziauddin utilizes his impact to compose a progression of articles for Pakistani papers, wherein he censures the Taliban for their savagery and brutality, just as their counter-intuitive translation of the *Quran*.

In 2009, Ziauddin utilizes his contacts with the BBC to orchestrate Malala to compose a progression of journal sections about her life under the Taliban. Malala expect a bogus name for security, and her journals become broadly perused in both Pakistan and the Western world. The Taliban, in the mean time, take steps to assault every one of ladies' schools that don't shut down. Hesitantly, Ziauddin closes down his schools, and Malala is compelled to remain at home from school, as well. Ziauddin takes his family to Islamabad for a quarter of a year, and when they return, they're calmed to locate their home pretty much unblemished. All through 2009, Malala keeps giving meetings in which she censures the Taliban for meddling with her training, and in 2010, she travels to Islamabad, joined by Shiza Shahid, a columnist and companion of her dad. In the city, Malala sees ladies with trainings and effective professions—this experience is immensely moving to her.

She meets significant heads of state, including the Prime Minister of Pakistan. As her notoriety develops, she keeps on contradicting the Taliban. The Taliban take steps to slaughter Malala on the off chance that she endures in her revilements. The account at that point turns up at ground zero to Malala's shooting. In the consequence of the endeavor on her life, Malala is hurried to a military emergency clinic, where a talented specialist, Colonel Junaid, attempts to spare her life. He prevails with regards to playing out a troublesome cerebrum medical procedure on Malala, and Malala from the outset is by all accounts making a full recuperation.

Malala awakens in the emergency clinic in England. Dr. Reynolds goes about as her legitimate gatekeeper while Ziauddin and Tor Pekai battle to travel to England. As she holds up in the medical clinic, Malala discovers that she's become universally well known after her shooting. Heads of state and VIPs send her roses, and different helpful people, motivated by her model; stand up against the Taliban's fierceness. Malala takes steps to utilize her notoriety to campaign for instruction and ladies' privileges on a worldwide scale.

The personal history finishes in 2013. Malala's family has relocated to England. Ziauddin functions as a specialist for both Pakistan's instructive framework and the board of trustees on training for the United Nations. Malala goes to class in Birmingham, concentrating on her investigations regardless of her gigantic acclaim. She feels all around

awkward in her new nation, not least since her cohorts think about her as a big name, not a colleague. By the by, Malala has risen up out of her shooting more grounded and more resolved to battle foul play than any time in recent memory. As the book closes, she reminds perusers that they are fortunate to be alive and to be cherished by God. Despite the fact that the Taliban attempted to slaughter her, she finishes up; they couldn't execute the worldwide campaign for instruction and uniformity among women.

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